

Managing The Causes Of Inter-Personal Conflicts Among Construction Professionals In Nigeria: A Review Of Architects And Builders Behaviour

Tope Femi Okuntade

Abstract—This paper contends that focusing on the efficient and effective ways of resolving interpersonal conflict between the Architects and Builder in the Nigerian construction industry is a major means of tackling the issues than emphasis on individuals personalities, and as such, the crucial goal should focus on preventing conflicts from arising during the initiation stage than trying to solve it when it occurs during the project execution. The paper focus majorly on the central tenets between the two professionals. However, win-lose situation, interdependence, budget allocations and lack of information were identified as the major factors contributing to the conflicts between the builder and the architects on a building projects.

Keywords— Conflicts, Interpersonal, initiation, construction industry, project execution

I. INTRODUCTION

Builders and Architect will have less conflict when they respect each others input, experience and professionalism. Conflict usually arises when architects act as the authority on cost and construction techniques or the Builder do the same regarding design, also conflict also arises when the designer major concern is the creativity in his design while on the other hand the builder is worried about the cost and time the architect creativity will consume, this raise a potential conflicting goal and affect the performance of the project. The greatest risk that comes from a poor relationship between an architect and builder is conflict in any project, when the two professionals fail to communicate effectively, the project can suffer from cost overrun, delays and most time project abandonment. These conflicts between this two are highly contagious and if not properly manage, can spread to other members of the projects. [1] construction professionals such as Builders, architects, engineers and quantity surveyors are the key participants of every construction project, they are typically drawn from different organizations to form a project team, each project team is thus, a mini society with a complex set of interrelated relationship requiring cooperation and collaboration from conception to completion of the construction project. This means the architect and builder in particular should work as a team but it is imminent that conflict may set in because the builder major concern is the process of the project (planning, budget etc) but because the builder and architect have different concerns or goal that could

lead to conflicts sometimes, the project must have a good balance between quality (architects concern), time (builders concern) and budget (builders concern). This means they have different goals and need and each expect to maximize their own benefits [2]. Construction projects are highly complex, involving interrelated activities like planning site operations, control, safety and management, any major events or a series of minor events in the project operation may create problems that could become construction conflict [1] concludes. The inability to manage the misunderstanding between these two professionals is a major foundation for conflict in the construction industry. In a situation where the function of the two professional is not uniquely defined in the conception of the contract, the thrive for dominance, control, management and supervision of the project becomes an interest and can lead to ambiguity where a builder is now performing the role of an architect and the architect performing otherwise, such controversy is another name for conflict. [3] also reveal that such problem in the industry stems from the ambiguity over who and who is ultimately responsible for managing design and construction of a project. However, in this regards architect and builders have stepped out beyond their traditional roles to provide a myriad of services outside their core responsibilities. It is a fact that no one person can conceive, design, construct, and commission a construction project however small, the project has to be divided into smaller tasks and these are assigned to specialist to avoid conflicts. But in a situation where one entity is assign all the responsibilities, team performance might be a problem. The concept of an entity taking all the responsibilities of the project has change, architecture has now been separated from construction where design is seen as a service, and building as a product. This paper will however focus mainly on how to manage the strain relationship between architects and builders and the causes of conflict between them.

II. WHAT IS CONFLICT?

The word conflicts brings to the mind image such as antagonism, struggles between parties, opposition processes and threats to cooperation but not all conflicts come in these forms especially in the construction industry, they come in form of need to be met or desires to be satisfied, disagreements to be settled and ideas to be shared that eventually leads to change of attitude feelings and perception[4]. Conflict was also expressed as a struggle

between at least two interdependent parties who perceive that incompatible goals, scarce resources and interference from others are preventing them from achieving their goals [5]. Conflict can also be described as an occasion where an individual or group feels negatively affected by another individual or group. Conflict is also a situation in which the parties are aware of the incompatibility of potential future positions and in which each party wishes to occupy a position which is incompatible with the wishes of the other (in this case the Architects and the builders). [6] cites an examples where conflicts occurs between parties whose tasks are interdependent, who are angry with each other, who perceive the other party as being at fault and whose actions can cause a business problem

A. PHASES OF ORGANIZATIONAL CONFLICTS

1. *Latent conflict*: latent or unstable conflict are the conflicts that exist whenever individuals, groups, organizations have difference that bother one or the other but those differences are not great enough to cause one side to act and alter the situation . Latent conflict may exist for very long period before it becomes visible and the conflict actor is conscious of it and behave accordingly. People may be in conflict without being aware that they are in conflict. Parties may have different ideas, values, personable and need which can create situation where others don't agree with their though or actions [7]

2. *Perceived conflict*: This kind of conflict exist when individuals and numbers of group feel the existence of a conflict, they are aware of past difference and solutions are proposed in accordance with previous experiment undertaken to prevent it from escalating. It is also a stage when people involved in conflict become fully aware that there is a conflict. The realization that there is a conflict but neither party is upset about it [8]

3. *Felt conflict*: From the word felt, the party now recognize that conflict exist unlike perceived conflict where they recognize that conflict exist but non of the party is bothered about it. In felt conflict, parties began to formulate strategies about how to deal with the conflict.

4. *Apparent or manifest conflict*: At this stage the conflicting parties show a variety of conflict behavior that appear in the from of competition or discussion or negotiation

5. *After math conflict*: The conflicting parties' search for the root of the problem and work to resolve it. If the results of the conflict management are satisfactory for all parties, an atmosphere of collaboration amongst the parties is expected to prevail. It takes place when there is some outcome of the conflict; such are resolution to or dissolution of the problem.

B. TYPES OF ORGANIZATIONAL CONFLICT

For clearer understanding of the various conflicts that exist, the types of organizational conflict will be explained briefly according to categories below

- Organizational conflict by parties
- Organizational conflicts by it direction
- Organizational conflict by its results

1) *Organizational conflicts by parties*

A. *Intrapersonal conflicts*

This kind of conflict occurs internally within the organization and individual due to likely incompatible goals. This incompatible goal can be as a result of

Positive conflicting goals- in this case, there are two more existing goals but achieving both at a time is the problem or rather when trying to achieve one may prevent the achievements of others

Negative conflicting goals: similar to positive conflicting goals but the difference is that one is positive while the other is negative. The individual is faced with two or more conflicting goals with all being negative, he/she must therefore choose one of them that is least harmful.

Conflict between achieving and not achieving the goals: this kind of conflict occurs when an individual has a goal which can lead to both positive and negative results. He/she becomes worried on whether the result will be positive or negative if embarked on.

B. *Inter-personal Conflict*

This form of conflict occurs between two or more individuals who have divergent or opposite outcomes (goals), attitudes, values or behavior and fail to share the same views, and have different interest or goals. Interpersonal conflicts also arise in a workplace due to natural differences in human personality, beliefs or work ethics. Co-workers may disagree over problem-solving tactics or shared resources, or employee may enter conflict with customers and clients, managers and supervised employees can also fall into routine disagreements over managerial style or workplace expectation.

C. *Intra-group Conflict*

This involves more people than intra-personal and inter-personal conflict: it is conflict between some or all of a group,,s members within the organization. It can also refer to conflicts between members of the same group or team. There are two main types of intra-group conflict: task conflict and relationship or emotional conflict.

D. *Inter-group Conflicts*

This is conflict that involves two or more groups within an organization. It is occurs between groups of people based on race, religion, ethnicity or levels of decision-making. These groups could be formal or informal, and the members of these

groups interact with each other for different purposes. These groups differ in goals, work activities, power, and prestige.

E. Intra-organizational Conflict

Intra-organizational conflict varies from organization to organization. Intra-organizational conflict occurs between parties within an organization. It can concern the structure of the organization, the location of formal authority and the way in which jobs are designed. Majority of inter organizational conflicts result in productivity of an organization rather than deterioration in performance.

2) *Organizational conflicts by its direction*

- *Horizontal organizational* - conflict takes place among parties in a certain group or organizational unit, or among different groups or organizational unit at the same level which has no authority over each other
- *Vertical organizational* conflict - occur among parties at different organizational levels whereby some employees are concerned with the tasks of implementation and have limited authority while other employees are specialized in the task of directing, controlling and decision making

3) *Organizational conflicts by its results*

- *Positive conflict* - conflict that is caused by minor difference. Conflict can be positive when 1. The value of conflict and difference are honored and respected and 2 issues are open and not masked 3 ideas not personalities are central 4. Emotions are managed and points of view expressed in a respected manner
- *Negative conflict* – The type of conflict cause damaged to individual and group as well as to organization. It occurs when two or more individuals are unable to work together because of hostility or rivalries between them. It occurs when 1. Conflicts are negative 2. Differences are not addressed 3. Expectations are not managed 4. Assumptions rather than fact are central to the alignments 5. The individual’s involved or affected don’t want to be part of the solution.

III. ARCHITECT AND BUILDER RESPONSE TO THE CAUSES OF INTERPERSONAL CONFLICT BETWEEN THEM

According to a survey conducted by finehomebuilding.com, two building professional were invited from Austin, Texas – Architect Paul DeGroot and Builder David Wilkes, they were asked to list the major problem and complains between the two of them. Table 1 shows the details of their response

A. *Dynamics of conflicts*

It is important to understand the dynamic of conflict before being able to think of solutions. This dynamics include the perception of the goal, perception of the other, view of the

others actions, definition of problem, communication, and internal group dynamics [9]. The dynamic are not limited but include the following elements :

Perception of the goal becomes a problem when success becomes competitive or doing better than the other guy. The focus is placed on the solution rather than attaining the goal.

- Perception of the other can create conflict when the attitude becomes “us versus them”. Similarly and differences are emphasized causing division within a group.
- View of others actions can be a problem when the situation is competitive instead of cooperation. Behavior can be suspicious in a competitive environment.
- Definition of problem can result in conflict when the size of the problem is escalated, issues are misconstrued, and original issues are lost.
- Communication in a competitive environment can cause mistrust and information may be withheld or may be lacking. Communication is not open and honest.
- Internal group dynamics can be negative when the group structure is centralized and rigid rather than safe and open. Conformity is emphasized and tasks dominate over the needs of the team.

TABLE I. ARCHITECT AND BUILDER RESPONSE TO THE CAUSES OF CONFLICT BETWEEN THEM

Bldr. David Wilkes (Builder) response	Arc. Paul DeGroot (Architect) response
Architects need to understand that all builders aren’t created equal	“custom” means everything to us and nothing to builders
We all know that architects like to stand out, so I’m sure they don’t like it if we builders lump them altogether regardless of their talent, design skills, and ability to work with others. It’s the same with builders they all have strength and weaknesses. To assume they are all the same is unfair to the client. That what architects sometimes do, though. Architects should find a few builders they trust and build a good relationship with them. Architects know their clients and should help them to select the builder who best fits their personality and who will best deliver on their expectations	It is well known that architects love to customize things, often to a fault. It’s our way of showing cleverness and creativity, and of proving our self worth. When our special little details are ignored or botched, our feathers get ruffled. When you see a curious detail on the plans, why don’t you ask us about it? Design is the architects calling card; neither he nor the homeowner who hired him wants to hear some builder say, ‘but that’s how we always do it’
Architects should select good contractors who can read drawings and execute their details. Choose the right builder, create the right team from the beginning, and this will not be a problem. If the clients insist on a cut rate builder, take the time to	Poor craftsmanship by builders makes us all look bad. We architects want to see parts fitting together precisely on all projects, regardless of budget. Sloppy work, especially on eyelevel things, really grates on us. Nothing says “I don’t care” like a

inspect the builders past projects to see the quality of his work. If its not up to standards, inform the clients that they will get what they pay for	big gap between trim boards, a door hung out of level, or a crooked AC vent. Builders who rush through the finish out the work that homeowners touch and see every single day have callbacks and disgruntlement that they and we both hear about
Architects need to provide detailed, complete drawings at the start of a project. If builders had their way, a complete set of drawing would be provided at the commencement of a project. This would allow the builder to see the whole project and make provisions for special details and other contingencies. In the real world, though, builders end up chasing details and changes from the architects offices. It would also help if architects provided drawings that reflected dimensions to frame and not to finishes – what I call” framer friendly drawings. It should not be the framers responsibility to make these decision onsite. This is particularly important on projects with high degree of complexity and several different finishes of various dimensions. Builders can read drawings, but they cannot read minds	Ok, I hear you. You look at our sketchy, incomplete drawings, and you think, “they re paid to draw, so why don’t they do more of it? The short answer is that we feel we re not paid enough to draw. Truth be told, we have a big time inferiority complex regarding our salaries compared to other professionals. Sometimes this even causes us to do silly things, like compare our fee to design a custom home to the commission a real estate agent gets to sell it. Knowing this, I would venture that many poor sets of plans start with a poor fee structure. Not all clients are willing to pay a complete set of drawing. Their preconceived notion of what an architect should cost may cover only the expense of an abbreviated “builder’s set” with just the basics. Ofcourse, though, it doesn’t help when we make things worse by designing an overly complex building that requires extra drawings
	Builders need to be more specific in their bid
You re right. A detailed cost estimate benefits everyone, and failing to offer enough details does make clients nervous. It all goes back to those drawings I was complaining about. Builders typically receive only schematics on which to base their bids, and it’s difficult for builders to give a detailed estimate based only on incomplete plans. Change order results mostly when clients select the cheapest builder, who has priced the project just to get the job. In those cases, client can end up paying more than they might have had they chosen a conscientious builder whose estimate was higher. The sad truth is that unrealistic estimate makes us all look bad. The best protection for both clients and honest builders is an architect who recommend good builders of equal quality	Today’s clients want to see bids that are well detailed, and they’re frustrated by bids that are vague or too general. I get asked all the time to help my clients make apples-to-apples comparisons of the various bid formats they receive. When builders and homeowner’s assumption don’t match up, the result is usually a change order. To the average Joe, a change order is a builder’s way of making extra money on something that should have been in the bid. Why cant builders do a better job of giving clients the derails they need to understand the scope and costs of their project fully?
	Too often, builders cut corners
This is what happens when a builder doesn’t properly supervise his subcontractors and the subcontractors start running the project. It’s important that architects select a builder whose superintendent will actively supervise the project. Cutting corners happens when clients select a builder based solely on price instead of looking at the overall company and processes	Bring up the subject of “builders who cut corners” at a gathering of architects and the discussion is unsure to get lively. Unfortunately, cutting corners often involved eliminating important things that homeowners don’t know much about. I see this quite a bit on my remodels, particularly in places like crawlspace and attics, where workers know that it’s unlikely anyone will check their work. Missing insulation, inadequate

	supports, missing injunction boxes, pinched ducts – you name it, I’ve seen it. Considering the overall cost of a house, these are nickel- and – dime items, but dodging these chump change costs can lead to big ticket repair down the road. Don’t builders get that?
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a. Source: finehomebuilding.com

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in this paper will adopt the results of data obtain from [10] survey, since the respondent in the research work consist mainly of the project managers and contractors. Architects and Builders will be avoided in this case to avoid sampling bias and accurate response from other construction professionals involved in a building project. The major causes of conflict generally covered in the Nigerian construction industry will be adopted and use to discuss on how to manage the conflict between the two professionals.

Table 2.0 present the result of data obtained from the response of the project managers and contractors regarding this causes of conflict in the Nigerian construction industry and in relation to the architects and builders

TABLE II. RESULTS OF DATAS OBTAINED FROM RESPONDENT

Causes of conflict Categories	Project managers RII	Contractors Rank	Contractors RII Rank
Task related causes	0.724	2	0.670 2
Competing goals	0.772	19	0.720 23
Incompatible interest	0.812	15	0.768 20
Differing principles	0.426	41	0.648 29
Incongruent values	0.386	42	0.232 45
Disagreement about strategy	0.746	20	0.768 20
Disagreement about execution	0.840	12	0.504 42
Diverse perspective	0.920	5	0.744 22
Lack of focus	0.666	24	0.744 22
Unclear objectives	0.800	16	0.760 21
Poor planning	0.880	9	0.760 21
Missed deadlines	0.720	22	0.720 23
External influence	0.819	1	0.788 1
Struggle for resources	0.734	21	0.644 27

Limited resources	0.734	21	0.920	9
A failing project	0.734	21	0.776	19
Win-lose scenario	0.974	1	0.632	31
Disgruntled client	0.933	4	0.880	13
Budget allocation	0.866	10	0.880	12
Lack of information	0.893	8	0.608	33
Interdependence	0.600	29	0.776	19
Ineffective process	0.906	6	0.960	4
Emotional trigger	0.713	3	0.765	3
Mixed feeling	0.920	5	0.912	10
Expectation	0.880	8	0.792	18
Prejudice	0.800	15	0.808	17
Perception of injustice	0.626	27	0.808	17
Jealousy	0.547	32	0.616	32
Retaliation	0.493	41	0.648	30
Anger	0.680	23	0.840	15
Non verbal signals	0.480	39	0.832	16
Stress buildup	0.920	5	0.680	25
Burnout	0.414	42	0.536	41
Fear	0.574	31	0.592	35
Harsh feedback	0.414	42	0.416	44
Feeling unappreciated	0.880	8	0.944	6
Distrust	0.814	14	0.904	11
Dissatisfaction	0.894	7	0.952	5
Feeling judged	0.894	7	0.960	4
Being isolate	0.626	27	0.696	24
Lack of trust	0.974	1	0.840	15
Behavioral antecedent	0.675	4	0.736	4
Miscommunication	0.626	27	0.944	6
Risk aversion	0.814	14	0.552	38
Self centered	0.866	10	0.984	3
Sarcasm	0.534	34	0.600	34

Competitive culture	0.854	11	0.856	14
Competitive personality	0.774	18	0.952	5
Demeaning language	0.827	13	0.952	5
Patronizing language	0.827	13	0.928	8
Condescending	0.814	14	0.936	7
Undermining expertise	0.827	13	0.928	8
Arrogance	0.787	17	1.000	1
Assumption	0.800	16	0.992	2
Complacency	0.547	31	0.936	7
Hostility	0.533	35	0.616	32
Passive Aggressiveness	0.467	40	0.584	36
Avoidance	0.800	16	0.936	7
Perfectionism	0.480	39	0.528	42
Inconsiderable behavior	0.494	38	0.536	41
Abusing authority	0.507	37	0.544	40
Desire to be right	0.520	36	0.552	39
Overdependence on others	0.534	34	0.560	38
Blaming or pointing fingers	0.547	37	0.568	33
Power struggle	0.560	32	0.496	43
Interrupting	0.574	39	0.552	31
Accusing	0.586	30	0.592	35
Rudeness	0.600	29	0.592	35
Unreliable	0.614	28	0.632	31
Failing to share credit	0.973	2	0.984	3
Micro financing	0.640	26	0.648	29
Incompetence	0.654	25	0.656	28
Complaining	0.666	24	0.664	27
Slow to adapt	0.680	23	0.672	26
No work no talk	0.666	24	0.680	25
Questioning others motive	0.960	3	0.984	3

a. Okuntade Tope Femi(2014)

V. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The results obtained from Table 2.0 are discussed below. Relative importance index (RII) is used to analyze the response obtained from the respondents with the following results. Under the categories of the causes of conflicts between the architects and builders, external influence was ranked first with a relative important index (RII) of 0.819 from the projects managers and 0.788 from the Contractors, likewise task related causes came second with RII of 0.724 and 0.670, emotional trigger was ranked third with RII of 0.713 and 0.765 in accordance with the project managers and the contractors respectively while behavior antecedence was ranked forth with RII of 0.675 and 0.736. Table 3.0 present the results in ascending order to the response obtained from the respondents .

TABLE III. RANKING CATEGORIES OF FACTORS

Category	Project managers RII	R	contractors RII	R	Overall RII	R
Task related cause	0.724	2	0.670	2	0.697	4
External cause	0.819	1	0.788	1	0.804	1
Emotional trigger	0.713	3	0.765	3	0.739	2
Behavioral antecedence	0.675	4	0.736	4	0.706	3

Categories	Project managers R	Contractors R	Overall R
External causes	0.819	1	0.804
Task related causes	0.724	2	0.745
Emotional trigger	0.713	3	0.725
Behavioral antecedent	0.675	4	0.673

Table 2.0 and 3.0 shows the arrangement of the response obtained from the project managers and contractors in relation to the causes of conflict among major professionals in the construction industry based on the categories, the individuals factors or variable will be discuss according to the rank in each categories in table 2. The results of the rated factors are explained below based on the highest importance index obtained from the respondents (as in Table 2.0)

A. Win-lose situation(index of 0.974)

Win lose are the possible outcome of a situation or conflicts involving two sides, which entails how each side perceives their outcome before the conflict. [11] explains win-lose situations as when only one side perceives the outcome as opposite or in a situation where each side gets part of what he or she wanted, but not as much as they might have gotten if they had used integrated bargaining. Win lose situation can contribute a gross difference between the architects and the builder. A situation where there is high competition between the two on the leadership of the project, hence both sides attempt to win and impress the client based on professional inferiority without much regards to the outcome of the projects or other parties but the consequences is that, one of

the party falls within their target range and the other party falls outside their target range.

B. Limited resources (index of 0.920)

Limited resources problem arises in construction projects when there are different limitations on the amount of resources available to the builder either due to the strain relationship with the architects or client or there are insufficient resources for the time allotted to the project. If resources are very scarce, people will always have to compete for them and the results will lead to conflicts. In the situation of architects and builders', we all know that they both depend on each other for the successful completion of a project or task but conflict may arise between the two in related to money, time and quality when one decision is affecting the other[12]. In this case the client is less concerned about who is right or wrong, all he cares about is delivery, and this can result in blame and negative conflicts

C. Failing projects (index of 0.776)

A failing project is a definition of conflict itself. It will be obvious to continue working on a doomed project. The inability of the builder and architect to clearly define their respective roles and responsibilities in a construction project can result in a failing project, errors and omissions. Sometimes when there are series of changes order from the architect, this might affect the budget of the builder in the other hand. Projects can also fail due to irrational, unclear or changing objectives to performance. Poor performance is the responsibilities of both the builder and the architects. The conflicting problem here is that neither the builder nor architect will want to admit responsibilities for failure and the inability to admit failure results in more problems which can spread to other members of the team.

D. Lack of information(Index of 0.893)

Information is a key factor between the two professionals. A lack of information can create uncertainty that can lead to stress and conflict between them. For instance, if a builder is waiting for an architect to deliver key information so he or she can complete a task on time, if the architect does not respond to the builder request, the builder may begin to worry about the outcome of using his own discretion at the expense of the architect. Hence, conflict sets in. another instance is when an architects and builder have different sets of information and have conflicting personalities and work approaches, it can create tension and lead to misunderstanding between the two.

E. Interdependence (index of 0.774)

Wikipedia explains interdependence as the mutual reliance between two or more group. According to [13,3] conflict also exist in a situation where interdependence people express differences in satisfying their individual needs and interests, and they experience interference from each other in accomplishing these goal. Most conflict is as results of interdependency, diverse perspectives, work habits, attention to details, communication practice or tone of expression.

These can affect the coordination of interdependent task between the architect and the builder

F. Budget allocation(index of 0.880)

In construction nearly everything is govern by the contract because if anything goes wrong, who will pay the extra cost. The architects are usually the one that sets the budgets and that usually cause conflict because architects are not involved in the day-to-day business of construction, which make them lose tracks of cost. When there's a conflict between the drawn plans and the written specification, the specification generally overrides the plans. Incomplete plans are the source of many conflict because the builder may have given a price but what exactly will the builder do at that price, when there is no detailed plans and specification which may not include painting, light fixtures etc these can affect s the budget allocation on the long run.

VI. APPROUCH IN MANAGING CONFLICTS BETWEEN THE TWO PROFESSIONALS

The following are the simple approach that can be use to prevent conflict between the builders and architects

A. Definition of Roles or professionalism

In any construction projects, preparation start with the architect, they initiate and create the project, they prepare the design concept and drawing, including specification and selections while the builders on the other hand interprets the drawing(purveyors of the project) by studying, dissecting, comprehending and assimilating the extensive drawing and specification provided. Conflict usually arises between the two when the builder begins to make design decisions and the architect begins to make construction decisions. These problems usually occur when the architects provides an incomplete documentations which allow the builders to start fixing or redesigning. Therefore, architects and builders will have less conflict on construction site when they respect each other unique roles which can only be enforced by professionalism and competency.

B. Communications

Communication here can be verbal or oral but in this concept, the paper focuses on both verbal and paper works. The design intention of the architects on paper must be fully understood by the builder, so that both parties do not have a separate vision on a project. The builder must also on the other hand consult with the architects during is interpretation when any discrepancies arises, the architect and the builder must respect each other perception so that the vision can be focus based and can reflect on the quality of works of tradesmen to ensure quality. Communication is however an imperative tools before and during construction in creating a positive relationship between the two professional since no design is perfect.

C. Executing the plans

The architects is usually the one that sets the budget which is usually a problem and need to be addressed because the one who face reality on site is the builder, this make the architect lose track of costs. For example an architect will tell a client that he will do project X for N50 million while the builder will tell the client that it will cost N100 million to do such project, this most times confuse the client on who's actually right, this can cause a strain relationship between the architects and the builder on the long run. Honesty and agreement between the two on this area is a key factor in the project

D. Right team, Right methodology or Approach

When a building project possesses the right team, conflict can be avoided. If a builder and architects who have worked together for years are employed for a project, the communication and understanding between the two will help the project because the two already understand each others flaws.

E. Competency

An experience professional be it architect or builder should be employed in a project and not a quack whose design or construction methodology can give room for conflict. The alteration in most design is caused most times by the architect's incompetency while the same applies to the builder. Competency can reduce conflict between the two professionals

VII. CONCLUSION

Collaborative relationships between architects and builders can be challenging due to difference in financial incentives, professional priorities and biases. And self interests. Architects and builders can find common ground and complement each others unique expertise when they respect each others roles which will prevent the architects questioning the ability of the builder and the builder questioning the knowledge of the architects.

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